

Quantitative structure-activity studies of imidazolidinone benzene sulfonamides : human β_3 -adrenergic receptor agonists acting as antiobesity drugs

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Substituted imidazolidinone benzene sulfonamides were reported to have high affinity for β_3 -adrenergic receptors of adiposites tissue. In order to establish an exact relationship between β_3 -adrenergic receptor agonistic activity and various quantifying parameters, these compounds were subjected to quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) analysis.

In recent years, it has been well established in several mammalian species and human that β_3 -adrenergic receptors play a major role in lipolysis and thermogenesis in adipose tissue, hence the search for specific β_3 -adrenergic receptors agonists capable of increasing metabolic rate by selective activation of these receptors is considered as a potentially effective approach for the treatment of obesity and diabetes¹. Many series of compound possessing β_3 -adrenergic receptors agonistic property have been reported in recent years, much of which belong to aryethanolamine category². The main problem with β_3 -adrenergic receptors is their cross reactivity at the β_1 - and β_2 -adrenergic receptors. Since obesity is a chronic condition and the drug therapy is likely to occur over prolonged period of time, there is a need to have very selective β_3 -adrenergic receptors agonists. Thus it is important to derive QSARs (Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship) which may be useful in proposing new compounds with enhanced activity and selectivity profile for β_3 -adrenergic receptors agonists. The main advantages in carrying out QSAR studies on this molecule are many, for example, it has only one substitution site, there is large variation in biological activity, doses are in nanomolar (nM) amounts, which help in obtaining highly significant QSAR equations. Since no such studies have been made for β_3 -adrenergic receptors agonists anywhere it appears of interest to carry out analysis of the reported imidazolidinone benzenesulfonamides³.

Results and discussion

From the listed compounds (Table 1) the software⁴ produced the following mono parametric QSAR equations (eq. (1) and eq. (2) using the data set

$$\log EC_{50} = 0.29 (\pm 0.056) RFr - 1.981 (\pm 0.190) \quad (1)$$

$$N = 17, r = 0.803, r^2 = 0.645, s = 0.284, F = 27.234$$

Table 1. QSAR parameters and biological activity ($-\log EC_{50}$) at the β_3 -adrenergic receptors of imidazolidinone benzene sulfonamides

Compd.	R	Fr ^a	MR ^b	Biological activity ($-\log EC_{50}$)		
				Obsd. ^c	Calcd. by eq. (1)	Calcd. by eq. (2)
1	CH ₃	0.77	5.65	-1.9318	-1.7569	-2.0476
2	n-C ₄ H ₉	2.51	19.61	-1.5686	-1.2505	-1.5032
3	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	3.05	2.51	-1.3223	-1.0934	-1.3121
4	n-C ₆ H ₁₃	3.59	29.10	-1.2557	-0.9363	-1.1210
5	n-C ₇ H ₁₄	4.13	3.31	-1.3010	-0.7791	-0.9299
6	n-C ₈ H ₁₇	4.67	39.21	-0.3424	-0.6220	-0.7388
7	Me(CH ₂) ₃ - CMe ₂ CH ₂	4.20	38.20	-0.7710	-0.7588	-0.7782
8	MeO(CH ₂) ₄	0.63	26.93	-1.8268	-1.8005	-1.2177
9	Ph(CH ₂) ₃	3.52	39.81	-0.6234	-0.9566	-0.7154
10	4-Cl Ph(CH ₂) ₃	3.58	45.74	-0.6435	-0.9392	-0.4841
11	3,4-diF PhCH ₂	1.68	32.11	-0.9779	-1.4921	-1.0157
12	CF ₃ (CH ₂) ₃	1.91	19.72	-1.2557	-1.4251	-1.4989
13	CF ₃ CF ₂ (CH ₂) ₃	2.96	23.93	-1.1463	-1.1196	-1.3347
14	c pent(CH ₂) ₃	4.19	38.03	-0.7559	-0.7667	-0.7848
15	c pent(CH ₂) ₂	3.65	33.13	-1.1140	-0.9188	-0.9759
16	c hex(CH ₂) ₃	4.73	42.93	-0.3979	-0.6045	-0.5937
17	c hex(CH ₂) ₂	4.19	38.03	-0.7634	-0.7613	-0.7848

^aHydrophobic constant value at position R, ^bMolar refractivity value at position R, ^cTaken from Ref. 3.

where, N = number of compounds, r = coefficient of correlation, F = degree of freedom and s = standard deviation.

$$\log EC_{50} = 0.039 (\pm 0.006) \text{RMR} - 2.268 (\pm 0.195) \quad (2)$$

$$N = 17 \quad r = 0.860 \quad r^2 = 0.739 \quad s = 0.243 \quad F = 42.526$$

Though the data contain 17 compounds³, still the correlation coefficient obtained were highly significant ($r = 0.803$ for eq. (1) and $r = 0.860$ for eq. (2)). The standard deviations were also very less (0.248 for eq. (1) and 0.243 for eq. (2)). If we look at statistical significance 'F-value', the values obtained were outstanding (27.234 for eq. (1) and 42.526 for eq. (2)) indicating the robustness of the QSAR equations. The coefficient of determination (r^2) was 0.645 and 0.739 for eqs. (1) and (2) respectively. The data within the parentheses, associated with coefficient value of the descriptors in the regression equation was very less indicating the high sensitivity of the equations. From eq. (1) it appears that a substituent such as octane or ethyl cyclohexane having large hydrophobicity constant value are advantageous i.e. hydrophobicity at R contributes positively towards the β_3 -adrenergic receptor agonistic biological activity. In addition, this equation also suggest that substituent at R should have less ionizable groups. The eq. (2) showed the significance of molar refractivity in drug receptors interaction. According to this model bulkier groups (octane or ethyl cyclohexane) are necessary to enhance the β_3 -adrenergic agonistic activity. Bulkier groups once attached to the receptors shows prolonged effect because it requires more time in detaching from the receptor site i.e. this descriptor determine both the affinity for the receptor and duration of action.

Compounds 6 and 16 are the potent compounds of the series and this is attributed to their large RFr and RMR constant values which are justified by the above discussion and QSAR models derived. Similarly, compound 1 (R = CH₃) has got very less RFr and RMR and therefore it is less potent. Compounds 6 and 14 have same number of carbon atoms in the molecule but former is more potent than later because of high RFr and RMR descriptors parameter value. This may be due to the presence of cyclopentane ring in compound 16. Looking into the positive contribution of both the independent biological parameters towards β_3 -adrenergic receptors agonistic activity, both the parameters were considered for deriving eq. (3).

$$\log EC_{50} = 0.128 (\pm 0.068) \text{RFr} - 0.027 (\pm 0.008) \text{RMR} - 2.297 (\pm 0.180) \quad (3)$$

$$N = 17 \quad r = 0.890 \quad r^2 = 0.792 \quad s = 0.225 \quad F = 26.708$$

This equation is more robust than eqs. (1) and (2) and explains better statistically the effect of independent parameters on β_3 -adrenergic receptors agonistic activity. Octane, which has both the characters, hydrophobicity as well as

molar refractivity, is most potent substituent in the series and fit quite well in the QSAR models. The calculated EC₅₀ values using eqs. (1), (2) and (3) is listed in Table 1. The observed vs calculated activity plots of eqs. (1), (2) and (3) is given in Figs. 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

Fig. 1. Graph between observed and calculated biological activity ($-\log EC_{50}$) calculated using eq. (1).

Fig. 2. Graph between observed and calculated biological activity ($-\log EC_{50}$) calculated using eq. (2).

Fig. 3. Graph between observed and calculated biological activity ($-\log EC_{50}$) calculated using eq. (3).

As the objective of the QSAR study is to derive the model that is optimally predictive and statistically strong we selected eq. (3) on the basis of its statistical significance i.e. having highest correlation coefficient ($r = 0.890$), coefficient of determination ($r^2 = 0.792$), F -test value (F -value = 26.708), and lowest standard deviation ($s = 0.225$). Thus the present study explores the physicochemical properties necessary for the drug to interact with β_3 -adrenergic receptors. This study also provides the basis for the selection of substituents in analogue drug design strategy.

Experimental

The essential requirements for QSAR studies are that the biological activities should be quantitative. Therefore, for the present purpose the result of β_3 -adrenergic activity reported by Naylor *et al.* was taken. They used β_3 -adrenergic receptors of Chinese Hamster Ovary. The title compounds triggered on the receptors in nanomolar quantity to release nor-adrenaline, hence activated the enzyme adenyl cyclase quantitatively, which was measured.

Out of the several descriptors tried, two namely, hydrophobic constant (Fr) and molar refractivity (MR) were found to give better relationship and hence these were selected in the present study. The physico-chemical parameters (RFr and RMR) were calculated from the compilation data of Hansch and Leo⁵, and multiparameters regression analysis was carried out on PC-486 using SYSTAT (Version 7.0) software for statistical studies to obtain sensitive and significant results⁵. All these explaining descriptors (independent variables) and the biological activity values as dependent variable (expressed as EC_{50} on nanomolar scale) for the compound under study are listed in Table 1. In order to obtain QSARs the multiple regression analysis (MRA) following a method of least square was considered. To obtain

quantitative models, the numbers of statistical parameters were obtained in conjunction with such calculation to access the significance of the derived results. These are the correlation coefficient (r), standard error of estimation (s), coefficient of determination (r^2) and F -value representing the ratio of the variance of calculated to observed activities. The \pm data within parentheses represents standard error of coefficient.

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